

Technical Marvels, Part 8: Historical Surveying Instruments

Early on, mathematics was of great importance for astronomy, navigation, time measurement, and surveying. As can be seen from contemporary textbooks by Benjamin Bramer, Levinus Hulsius and Leonhard Zubler, the main focus in the 17th century was on measuring distances and heights. The “geometrical instruments” resembled sectors and some had a crossbar and a semicircular protractor. Some surveying instruments have survived in museums.

By Herbert Bruderer

In the third part of his work *Apollonius Cattus*, Benjamin Bramer speaks of the “geometrical triangulation instrument”, which makes it possible to measure heights, depths, lengths and widths. He dedicated his work to Landgrave Wilhelm von Hessen. The distance meter looks like a sector with two legs, an additional folding rule and sights (see Fig. 1). Sometimes, as shown in his *Trigonometria planorum mechanica*, it is combined with a protractor and placed on a tripod. It was used to determine the height of towers (see Fig. 2), the depth of wells and the position of clouds (see Fig. 3). The tool was also suitable for determining the area of polygons (see Fig. 4). Plumb bobs were also used for vertical shafts in a mine. Surveying was often utilized in the service of war. Sectors were each provided with numerous scales. Bramer was the brother-in-law of Jost Bürgi, who created the logarithms independently of John Napier.

Fig. 1: Distance measurement with a triangulation instrument. Source: Benjamin Bramer: *Apollonius Cattus*, Part 3 (Chapter 4)

Fig. 2: Determining the height of a tower with a triangulation instrument. Source: Benjamin Bra-mer: Apollonius Cattus, Part 3 (Chapter 10)

Fig. 3: Determining the height of a cloud with a triangulation instrument. Source: Benjamin Bra-mer: Apollonius Cattus, Part 3(Chapter 17)

Fig. 4: Calculation of a polygon with a triangulation instrument. Source: Benjamin Bramer: Apollonius Cattus, Part 3 (Chapter 5)

Leonhard Zubler from Zurich dedicated his work *Novum Instrumentum Geometricum* to Duke Friedrich von Württemberg. He presents his “geometrical instrument”, which consists of a sector with hinged folding rule and a semicircular protractor (semicircular disc with compass) (see Fig. 5). There are also military applications in his textbook (see Fig. 6). Other examples include measuring the height of towers (Fig. 7) or determining the height of mountains. Zubler explains that Thales of Miletus is said to have invented this “geometria” in Egypt and brought it to Greece. He also gives instructions on how to build the triangulation instrument.

Fig. 5: Surveying with a geometrical instrument (semicircular disc with protractor and compass and sector with three legs). Source: Leonhard Zubler: Novum instrumentum geometricum (page 18)

Fig. 6: Distance measurement with a geometrical instrument (sector with semicircular protractor). Source: Leonhard Zubler: Novum instrumentum geometricum (page 16)

Fig. 7: Determining the height of a tower with a geometrical instrument (sector with semicircular protractor). Source: Leonhard Zubler: *Novum instrumentum geometricum* (page 25)

In *Theoria et Praxis Quadrantis Geometrici*, Levinus Hulsius introduces the use of the geometrical quadrant (see Fig. 8). It can be used to determine the height of towers, columns and trees, for example (see Fig. 9). Distances and the width of rivers can also be calculated. The instrument was also utilized to compute the length of shadows. For comparison: The back of astrolabes (two-dimensional models of the sky) often have a shadow square. This can be used to measure the height of mountains, for example. The term “umbra recta” means straight shadow, “umbra versa” stands for the reversed shadow. In his work, Hulsius also describes a mathematical device with a compass.

Fig. 8: Geometrical quadrant, an aid for measuring height and distance. Source: Levinus Hulsius: *Theoria Et Praxis Quadrantis Geometrici* (page 9)

Fig. 9: Determining the height of a column with a geometrical quadrant. Source: Levinus Hulsius: *Theoria Et Praxis Quadrantis Geometrici* (page 30)

Acknowledgments

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Further reading

- Bruderer, Herbert: Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter Oldenbourg, Berlin/Boston, 3rd edition 2020, volume 1, 970 pages, 577 figures, 114 tables, <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110669664>
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Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter, 3. Auflage 2020

Milestones in Analog and Digital Computing, Springer, 3rd edition 2020

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This post is the eighth in a series that presents selected technical marvels from the fields of computing technology, mathematics, astronomy, surveying, time measurement, looms, and automatons (automaton figures, chess-playing machines, musical automatons, automaton writers, drawing automatons, automaton clocks, picture clocks, globes, and historical robots). The examples are largely from the 15th to 20th centuries and do not claim to be exhaustive. In particular, artifacts are included for which high-quality illustrations are available. Most of the objects come from Europe, with a few from Africa, America, Asia, and Australia. The order is predominantly chronological. Famous names such as Archimedes, Hipparchus, Heron of Alexandria, Leonardo da Vinci, Galileo Galilei, John Napier, Jost Bürgi, Blaise Pascal, Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz, and Charles Babbage are associated with these works. In some cases, however, the inventors are unknown (e.g. abacus, Antikythera Mechanism, yupana, quipu); see [Technical Marvels, Part 7: Musical Clocks and Organs – Communications of the ACM](#)

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